

Desk Research

Green skills and the future of employability: Aligning
higher education with labour market trends

August 2025

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INTRODUCTION

This research focuses mainly on how the job market will change in the face of the green transition, which skills will emerge as fundamental for the future labour market and how higher education can adapt to align with these trends. Many institutions at the European and international levels have dealt with these issues, including the European Commission, the Council of the European Union, the World Economic Forum (WEF), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

The EU has introduced some key policy initiatives and documents to support and promote environmental protection and the green transition. The flagship initiative of the first von der Leyen presidency is the European Green Deal (EGD), a strategy launched in 2019 with the overarching aim of making the EU climate neutral in 2050 (European Commission, 2019). In this context, in 2021, the EU adopted the European Climate Law, writing into law the climate neutrality goal set in the European Green Deal and setting an intermediate target of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. To achieve these decarbonisation objectives, emissions must be reduced in all sectors, from industry and energy to transport and farming (Regulation (EU) 2021/1119). Moreover, the European Union has adopted the European Skills Agenda. It is the EU's 5-year plan, which aims to equip individuals and businesses with the skills they need for life and work. One of the plan's objectives is to promote the skills needed for the green transition, contributing to the goals of the EGD (European Commission, 2020a).

The green transition will present both opportunities and challenges to the labour market: some jobs will disappear, new ones will be created, while others will drastically change. According to WEF's Future of Jobs Report published in January 2025, "Climate change adaptation is expected to be the third-largest contributor to net growth in global jobs by 2030" (WEF, 2025). Similarly, the ILO states that "it is clear that, across all countries, green jobs are forecast to be a source of employment growth, and a particularly important one in developing countries" (ILO, 2019). Some sectors will be most affected by the green agenda, such as renewable energy, environmental goods and services, and construction.

As a consequence of the green transition, the skills required to perform jobs in the future will look very different from those needed for the current labour market, and as such, resulting in skill gaps among the population. In the "Council conclusions on skills and competences for the green transition," the institution recognises that "The skills and competences and skill sets required for the green transition are diverse in nature and continue to emerge and to be defined" (The Council, 2023). In general, most new green occupations require new, highly scientific knowledge and technical skills. However, **not only will the green transition require sector-specific and technical skills (such as environmental engineering and sustainable energy), but also lifelong and transversal skills (such as adaptability, communication, creative and analytical thinking).** Higher education institutions are rightly positioned to cultivate and recognise both.

HIGHER EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY

The education sector, particularly the higher education sector, is also affected and has a significant impact on sustainable development. On the one hand, higher education institutions have a noteworthy carbon footprint and can negatively affect the environment through various practices, including high levels of waste and energy consumption and large-scale campus operations. For example, the intensive use of fossil fuels, the procurement of materials and equipment for research or administrative purposes, and the commuting of staff and students have a significant impact on the overall carbon footprint of an HEI (Kiehle et al., 2023). International student mobility programmes represent another area with a stronger effect on the environment, as they directly contribute to the increase in greenhouse gas emissions. One of the most ambitious analyses of the carbon footprint of Erasmus+ was a report published by the Finnish National Agency in 2021, which put the 2017 emissions related to mobility at around 421,433 tons of carbon dioxide (EDUFI, 2021). To make a comparison, this is almost double the amount of emissions produced by Formula 1 in 2018 (for more information, refer to [this article by EUF](#)). More recently, in the 2024 results of the Climate Action Barometer (CAB), the International Education Sustainability Group (IEGS) showed that the total carbon footprint of student and staff mobility in the academic year 2022/2023 of the CAB group amounted to 691,191 tons of carbon dioxide (IEGS, 2025).

However, universities and other educational institutions are also drivers of sustainable innovation, thanks to the introduction of sustainability strategies and practices on campus, research programmes focused on the green transition and training for students and staff. From this perspective, sustainability reporting is a useful tool for higher education institutions to communicate their commitment to sustainability and to inspire members of the university community to adopt similar sustainable practices (Haynes, 2023).

Moreover, education is key to improving people's capacity to understand and address environmental and development issues. **Through formal, informal, and non-formal education, people can acquire the skills and competencies necessary for the future.** While formal learning usually happens through structured educational programmes, informal and non-formal learning usually takes place outside of education and training institutions and can also occur involuntarily. For instance, students learn formally when they attend a course offered by their university, whereas they learn non-formally when they participate in volunteering activities in their community or when they come across environmental messages across their university campus, which can lead to subliminal or subconscious learning.

EXAMPLES AND RELEVANCE OF GREEN COMPETENCIES

Various institutional reports focusing on skill needs for the green transition identify the green transversal skills that will be necessary in the future. Some of these are already valued by employers today, but they will gain more relevance with the emergence of green jobs. The main skills identified as crucial for the future are listed below in alphabetical order.

Adaptability, resilience and flexibility

As the future job market and the green transition are expected to bring changes to the labour market, workers of the future will need to be capable of adapting to uncertainty and responding appropriately to new circumstances.

“Required across the labour force: resilience **to see through the changes required**. [...] Adaptability and transferability skills to enable workers to **learn and apply the new technologies and processes** required to green their jobs.” (ILO, 2019)

“At an aggregate level across all growing and declining roles, **resilience, flexibility and agility skills** are the most significant differentiators between growing and declining job roles, **ranking higher in both importance and proficiency for growing roles**.” (WEF, 2025)

Communication and persuasion

The changes associated with the green transition will affect not only employees in specific sectors, but also the broader population. Interpersonal competencies are therefore needed to ensure that their positive effects are spread as much as possible.

“Soft skills, such as communication and persuasion, are becoming more important in profiles across sectors and demonstrate the proliferation of service-oriented activities (for example, in waste management). Such skills help **communicate and educate producers and consumers** about the merits of adopting green solutions or practices and contribute to **establishing green visions or mindsets** among the population, workers, and organisations.” (Cedefop, 2023)

Creative and analytical thinking

In the future, workers will need to tackle ever more complex problems and find innovative solutions. Their creative and analytical thinking skills will be fundamental for this goal.

“Required in medium to high-skilled occupations: **Analytical thinking** (including risk and systems analysis) **to interpret and understand the need for change and the measures required**.” (ILO, 2019)

“The skills categories that are projected to grow the most in demand according to the projections developed by the OECD between 2019 and 2030 with the implementation of the Fit for 55 policy

include: **interacting with computers; thinking creatively; analysing data** [...] for which demand will grow as a result of the technological adoption.” (OECD, 2023)

“They [Green Skills] also relate to transversal skills needed to enable **critical thinking, systems thinking, problem solving and innovation.**” (The Council, 2023)

“As in the two previous editions of this report, **analytical thinking remains the top core skill for employers,** with seven out of 10 companies considering it as essential.” (WEF, 2025)

Environmental awareness, respect and stewardship

As environmental sustainability becomes a central priority across different sectors, workers will need to align with its principles and promote it in their jobs.

“**Evaluate environmental impact** of personal behaviour: adopt a **sustainability-oriented mindset** in your daily life and reflect on your personal ecological attitude and on the environmental impact of your behaviour.” (ESCO Publications, 2022)

“Required across the labour force: environmental awareness and respect; **willingness to learn about sustainable development.**” (ILO, 2019)

“Environmental sustainability competence comprises the **knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that are critical to promoting environmental sustainability.**” (OECD, 2023)

“Networks and cybersecurity and environmental stewardship [...] rank among the top 10 skills expected to increase significantly in use by 2030, yet they are not currently considered core skills for most organizations. [...] A **growing focus on environmental stewardship** as a critical skill reflects an evolving alignment between business strategies and sustainability objectives.” (WEF, 2025)

Problem-solving

When tackling complex problems, future workers will need to possess a solution-oriented attitude in order to transform their innovative ideas into concrete results.

“Examples of Work Activities skills that are estimated to grow the most in demand include: [...] “**making decisions and solving problems**”.” (OECD, 2023)

“They [Green Skills] also relate to transversal skills needed to enable critical thinking, systems thinking, **problem solving and innovation.**” (The Council, 2023)

Teamwork and collaboration

As the problems become more complex, more people will be involved in their resolution. This will require workers to be able to cooperate effectively with colleagues coming from diverse fields and sectors.

“Soft skills that facilitate **working collaboratively across functions within organisations and with an expanding range of stakeholders** are becoming more important.” (Cedefop, 2023)

“Required across the labour force: teamwork skills, reflecting the **need for organizations to work collectively** on tackling their environmental footprint.” (ILO, 2019)

In summary, according to the WEF’s Future of Jobs Report, the skills projected to grow in importance more rapidly are technological, as well as **creative thinking, resilience, and flexibility. Environmental stewardship and analytical thinking are also on the rise.** Increasing skill demands in environmental stewardship skills are particularly evident in the Oil and Gas and Chemical and Advanced Materials industries (WEF, 2025).

The OECD also stresses the weight of attitudes beyond skills. For instance, recognising the relevance of promoting environmental sustainability is essential to motivating individuals to integrate sustainable practices into their daily lives as consumers (OECD, 2023). According to the ILO, general soft skills are needed by all workers, while more technical ones may be required for medium to high-skilled occupations (ILO, 2019). The OECD also indicates other “transformative competences for 2030”, not only linked to the green transition but to the transformation of the labour market in general: creating new values, reconciling tensions and dilemmas and taking responsibility (OECD, 2019).

Additionally, initiatives from the private and civil society sectors have also dealt with the growing need for new skills. For instance, the report “Green Soft Skills and Green Emerging Jobs in the Youth Sector” of the E+ project Green Youth Employability illustrates the results of a survey conducted among young people, youth workers, staff within public entities, experts in environmental sustainability and HR professionals. The results show that **the most relevant soft skills for green jobs are critical thinking, environmental awareness, systematic thinking, teamwork, and adaptability,** directly corresponding to the ones identified by international organisations and institutions (GYE, 2025).

THE EMPLOYERS' PERSPECTIVE

Employers have also reiterated the need for new skills to meet their demands as they transition to a more sustainable working culture. Emerging Group, a hub of knowledge on employability, published the GEURS 2025 report, a graduate employability report, drawing from a global survey of over 13,000 recruiters. It states that **sustainability is no longer a specialised field and that green skills also include competencies such as adaptability, collaboration, problem-solving, and environmental policy awareness** (in line with the institutional positions). According to the recruiters surveyed, these skills transitioned from desirable to mandatory (Emerging, 2025).

The WEF's "Future of Jobs Report 2025" brings together the perspectives of over 1,000 leading global employers, collectively representing more than 14 million workers across 22 industry clusters and 55 economies from around the world (WEF, 2025). At the same time, a 2022 Eurochambers survey, collecting inputs from 51 national and regional chambers from 15 European countries, highlighted that "more than a quarter of respondents cite the need to update school programmes to meet the labour market priorities. This should be done in accordance with forecasting the skills necessary for the green transition; thus, the development of effective skills intelligence tools is critical" (Eurochambres, 2022).

Furthermore, according to LinkedIn's Global Green Skills Report 2024, "as employers strive to hit sustainability targets, they are driving up demand for green talent in most countries. In 2023, 7.3% of job postings on LinkedIn were for a green job or required green skills. This year [2024], that figure rose to 7.7%" (LinkedIn, 2024). On a smaller scale, according to a ManpowerGroup survey, six out of 10 Belgian employers are already recruiting 'green' profiles or developing the skills needed for the ecological transition. Still, one in two companies is having difficulty finding them on the job market (ManpowerGroup, 2023). However, both LinkedIn and ManpowerGroup refer more specifically to the technical green skills (not the soft ones) required by future jobs.

THE ROLE OF HEIS IN SKILLS DEVELOPMENT AND RECOGNITION

Higher education plays a dual role in cultivating these competencies and in recognising them, even when they have been acquired through non- and informal learning.

First, HEIs can provide the settings where students develop and practice their green soft skills. For instance, universities can offer dedicated academic courses on sustainability or integrate environmental topics across various subjects, embedding the issue into the broader curriculum. Educational institutions can also foster student engagement by offering opportunities to cooperate in the local Green Office or promoting other sustainability-focused student organisations and local initiatives.

In 2021, the European University Association (EUA) conducted a comprehensive survey of 372 universities to collect the greening measures and initiatives being implemented. The findings reveal that universities are increasingly encouraging greening practices in several areas, including student and staff mobility, learning and teaching activities, and campus operations. Notably, all institutions implement initiatives aimed at improving sustainable mobility and commuting, although these measures are more likely to be encouraged rather than compulsory. When assessing the impact of these initiatives, the majority of respondents believe that they helped create “real-life” learning opportunities for students, and enhanced awareness and changed behaviour of students (either strongly or to some extent) (Stöber et al, 2021).

The recognition of skills acquired through non-formal and informal education has also been a key topic of discussion in recent years. In 2012, the Council published a recommendation encouraging Member States to establish national arrangements for its validation (The Council, 2012). According to an Eurydice report of the European Commission, there is an **increasing willingness from higher education institutions to recognise skills acquired through non-formal and informal education** (European Commission / EACEA / Eurydice, 2024). Validation opportunities have also increased in the labour market and the third sector. In 2018, arrangements for skills validation provided by labour market actors were only available in 17 member states and not throughout the EU (European Commission, 2020b). However, there has been a significant increase in the number of countries with validation arrangements in the labour market between 2018 and 2023: In 2023, two-thirds of countries had arrangements in place in both the labour market and the third sector (European Commission and Cedefop, 2024). This trend is depicted in the Figure below.

Lastly, some academics have also focused their research on the topic. For instance, “Foundations for a green economy: how institutions shape green skills”, an academic article by Busemeyer et. al., examines how green skills are formed both in OECD and low- and middle-income countries, highlighting the role of the institutions and VET regimes in their development (Busemeyer et. al, 2025).

Figure 4. Evolution in the number of countries with validation arrangements

Source: European Inventory Reports (2023, 2018, 2016).

Nb: Data broken down by sector were collected for the first time in the 2016 Inventory.

CONCLUSION

In the future, the skills required by an evolving and greening job market will be different. These skills are both technical, typically acquired through formal learning, and transversal via non-formal and informal learning. Higher education institutions have the opportunity to support the development of both types of skills for the future. This can be achieved, first, by creating additional environments where they can be practised. Second, HEIs can integrate these competencies into the students' educational journey by improving the mechanisms for their recognition.

Travelling sustainably to their mobility destination represents one informal setting for students to enhance and practice these skills. As such, a major objective of the Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel project, coordinated by the EUF, is to improve students' opportunities to develop more environmentally sustainable habits during their mobility, as well as to change their view of the mobility destination as an experience that is transformative in itself. In the context of the project, the [SET Green Skills Repository](#) identifies the list of green transversal skills applied and/or acquired by students when travelling sustainably. Many of these correspond to the ones identified by institutions and employers as necessary for the future.

Through sustainable travel, mobile students have the opportunity to gain distinctive experiences that demonstrate and cement their green skills, which are required by the future job market. **The experience of travelling sustainably can transform them into conscious agents aware of their personal development and of how this will impact their professional life.** When seeking a job, they will be able to demonstrate the key skills required by providing a concrete case of their sustainable travel, for example, in their motivation letter, interview, or via a “green travel supplement” to their diploma. At the same time, employers are increasingly likely to validate these skills, developed through informal and non-formal learning.

Whether students choose a career in the green and sustainability sector in the future or not, we hope they will use their sustainable skills in other areas of life. Although this prediction has yet to come true, it represents a positive step towards a greener future and a continuation of the sustainable journey taken by these students.

GLOSSARY

TERM	DEFINITION	SOURCE, YEAR
Competence	Demonstrated ability to use knowledge, know-how, experience and – job-related, personal, social or methodological – skills, in work or learning situations and in professional and personal development.	Cedefop, 2014
Core skills/Core employability skills	Non-vocational, non-technical skills or competencies that are needed to perform at work and in society. They apply to work generally, rather than being specific to an occupation or industry. Core employability skills include the ability to work with others and in teams; the ability to solve problems and use technology; communications skills; and learning-to-learn skills. Core skills are also called generic skills, key competencies, key skills, portable skills, soft skills and transferable skills.	ILO, 2019
Formal learning	Acquisition of knowledge, know-how, information, values, skills and competences in an organised and structured environment in terms of learning objectives, time or resources (e.g. an education or training institution or a company).	Cedefop, 2014
Green job	Occupation supporting the transition to a greener economy and society.	Cedefop, 2014
Green skills	The knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to live in, develop and support a society which reduces the impact of human activity on the environment	Cedefop, 2012
Green transition / transition to the green economy	Process of transforming the system of production, distribution and consumption of wealth towards a sustainable development model (enhancing energy and resource efficiency, reducing carbon emissions and pollution, protecting biodiversity and ecosystems) to improve human well-being and social inclusion, limit environmental risks and preserve natural assets.	Cedefop, 2014
Green travel	Travel that uses low-emissions means of transport for the main part of the travel, such as bus, train, bike or car-pooling.	European Commission, 2025

Greenhouse gas	A gas that contributes to the natural greenhouse effect. The Kyoto Protocol covers a basket of six greenhouse gases (GHGs) produced by human activities: carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, hydrofluorocarbons, perfluorocarbons and sulphur hexafluoride	European Environment Agency
Informal learning	Learning resulting from daily activities and experiences which is not organised or structured in terms of objectives, time or learning support; it may be unintentional from the learner's perspective.	European Commission, 2025
Key competences	The basic set of knowledge, skills and attitudes which all individuals need for personal fulfilment and development, employability, social inclusion, sustainable lifestyle, successful life in peaceful societies, health-conscious life management and active citizenship, as described in the Council Recommendation 2018/C 189/01 of 22 May 2018 on key competences for lifelong learning.	European Commission, 2025
Labour market/job market	Real or virtual meeting point, within an economy or area, where people selling their labour (workers) negotiate and may reach an agreement with those who buy it (employers).	Cedefop, 2014
Non-formal learning	Learning which takes place through planned learning activities where some form of learning support is present, but which is not part of the formal education and training system.	European Commission, 2025
Retraining/reskilling	Training enabling individuals to acquire new skills, giving access either to a new occupation or to new professional activities	Cedefop, 2014
Skill	Ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems.	Cedefop, 2014
Transversal (soft; life) skills	Include the ability to think critically, be curious and creative, to take initiative, to solve problems and work collaboratively, to be able to communicate efficiently in a multicultural and interdisciplinary environment, to be able to adapt to context and to cope with stress and uncertainty. These skills are part of the key competences.	European Commission, 2025
Upskilling	Short-term targeted training typically provided following initial education or training, and aimed at supplementing, improving or updating knowledge, skills and competences.	Cedefop, 2014

Vocational Education and Training (VET)	Education and training which aims to equip young people and adults with knowledge, skills and competences required in particular occupations or more broadly on the labour market. It may be provided in formal and nonformal settings, at all levels of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), including tertiary level, if applicable.	European Commission, 2025
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